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Abstract

The purpose of this document is to detail the architecture and the specifications for cyber-security and data-privacy bricks, including solutions for privacy-friendly-authentication, role-based Identity and Access Management and cyber-security situation awareness.

Legal Disclaimer

The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
4G	4th Generation cellular communication
5G	5th Generation cellular communication
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Certificate Authority
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Messages
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CoA	Course of Actions
CP	Certification Policy
CPE	Common Pattern Enumeration
CPM	Container Distribution Message
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CVE	Common Vulnerability Exposure
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
EC	European Commission
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Initiative
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
ITS-S	ITS-Station
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PO	Project officer
PoTi	Position and Time
RSU	Roadside Unit
SP	Security Policy
TIP	Threat Intelligence Platform
WP	Work Package

Table 1 - Abbreviations and Acronyms

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Executive Summary

The aim of the ICT4CART project is to design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation. It focuses on four high-value use cases: Smart Parking & IoT services, dynamic adaptation of vehicle automation level based on infrastructure information, intersection crossing (urban) & lane merging (highway), and Cross Border Interoperability. Work Package 3 (WP3) builds on the findings of WP2, which includes the specification of the use cases (Deliverable D2.1), the analysis of market needs (D2.2) and the system requirements (D2.3). Within deliverable D3.1 of WP3, the ICT4CART Reference Architecture has been developed. It is the basis for the subsequent Tasks 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4, where the key aspects of Flexible Networks, IT Environment, and Cyber-Security & Data Privacy are refined.

Deliverable D3.4 aims to detail and specify the ICT4CART cyber-security and data privacy architecture, based on the ICT4CART Reference Architecture (D3.1). The Introduction in Section 1 describes the purpose and the aims of the deliverable. Section 2 contains the enumeration of the existing standards and regulations, which apply in terms of cyber-security and data privacy in the European Union and also those applied in the automotive sector. It is followed by Section 3, 4 and 5 detailing the ICT4CART architecture of respectively the cyber-security supervision and the data privacy service. These sections are organized in the same way: the role of the service is described; the actors interacting with it are presented; the functional architecture is illustrated and the functional blocks are detailed; the support capabilities and the external interfaces are depicted. In order to highlight the interactions between actors and both services, Section 6 gathers sequence diagrams of actions related to the supervision centre and the data privacy service. Sections 7 and 8 aim to provide all the requirements enumerated in section “Cyber-security and Data Privacy Requirements” (D2.3) are effectively covered by the architecture proposed. Finally, Section 9 concludes the document with a summary of the main aspects of the ICT4CART cyber-security and data privacy architecture.

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

Today, significant and rapid advances in both telecom and IT industries can be accredited to fast-growing disruptive technologies. Amongst these, the ETSI ITS G5 technology appears to be quite mature. Moreover, the 5G technology is evolving rapidly, while LTE-Vehicle (LTE-V) features low cost and rapid deployment since it can utilize existing base stations. In the light also of the above, several ICT challenges related to connectivity, data management, cyber-security and ICT infrastructure architectures still play a significant role and need to be addressed in order to enable road vehicle automation. Thus, it is of utmost importance for the vehicle automation to work on the direction of advancing the digital and ICT infrastructure, taking also into consideration the limitations in both resources and investments, in the physical transport infrastructure.

ICT4CART aims to address the gaps to deployment bringing together key players from automotive, telecom and IT industries, to shape the ICT landscape for Connected and Automated Road Transport and to boost the EU competitiveness and innovation in this area.

The main goal of ICT4CART is to design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation (up to L4) addressing existing gaps and working with specific key ICT elements, namely hybrid connectivity, data management, cyber-security, data privacy and accurate localization. ICT4CART builds on high-value use cases (urban and highway), which will be demonstrated and validated in real-life conditions at the test sites in Austria, Germany and Italy. Significant effort will be put also on cross-border interoperability, setting up a separate test site at the Italian-Austrian border.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This deliverable will elaborate further on the functional architecture of both supervision and data privacy services which have been broached in deliverable D3.1 – Reference Architecture.

It relies on the use case definition (T2.1) and the requirement specification report (T2.3). D3.4 will be used as an input for the WP6 dedicated to the developments and the integration of cyber-security solutions for enhanced cyber-security supervision and data privacy for automated driving purposes.

1.3 Targeted audience

This deliverable is addressed to any interested reader (i.e., Public dissemination level) and especially to the one who has read the D3.1 – Reference Architecture and who wants further information on the cyber-security and data privacy architecture proposed by the ICT4CART project.

2 Existing standards, regulations, and project initiatives

This chapter refers to existing standards, regulations and projects that drive the definition of the architecture of cyber-security and privacy services.

2.1 Certificate Policy for Deployment and Operation of European C-ITS

The Certificate Policy for Deployment and Operation of European Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (CP) regulates the generation and usage of certificates within the C-ITS trust domain. It provides vital information on the certificates used for C-ITS. The CP states the usage of several different certificates to mask the identity of a vehicle sending out a C-ITS message. This document is part of the Annex of the COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) .../...of 13.3.2019 supplementing Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the deployment and operational use of cooperative intelligent transport systems.

2.2 Security Policy & Governance Framework for Deployment and Operation

The Security Policy and Governance Framework for Deployment and Operation of European Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (SP) regulate the organization of C-ITS Security Elements. In the first part it describes the roles of the several authorities needed for the communication security. While in the second part it describes the risks and rules for C-ITS Security. This document is part of the Annex of the COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) .../... of 13.3.2019 supplementing Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the deployment and operational use of cooperative intelligent transport systems.

2.3 ETSI standards

The ETSI has proposed many standards related to Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS). The following figure depicts the C-ITS architecture proposed by the ETSI. Among the two cross-layers, the security layer is devoted to secure communications between ITS-S and provides security services to the communication stack. The second one, the management layer controls the communication stack with respect to the application requirements. The facilities layer is similar to session, presentation and application layers of the OSI model [1]. The Networking and Transport layer manages data transport between ITS-S. This layer is similar to network and transport layers of the OSI model. The access layer (equivalent to the OSI model physical and data link layers) manages wired and wireless access technologies of ITS-S, such as IEEE 802.11p, IEEE 802.3 and IEEE 802.11a. The applications layer represents the layer where applications run.

Figure 1 – ETSI C-ITS architecture model

In this deliverable, we focus on the security layer and more specifically we study the six following ETSI standards resumed in Table 2.

ETSI Standards	Title	Version used in this deliverable
ETSI TR 102 893	<i>Threat, Vulnerability and Risk Analysis (TVRA)</i>	V 1.2.1
ETSI TS 102 731	<i>Security Services and Architecture</i>	V 1.1.1
ETSI TS 103 097	<i>Security header and certificate formats</i>	V 1.3.1
ETSI TS 102 940	<i>ITS communications security architecture and security management</i>	V 1.3.1
ETSI TS 102 941	<i>Trust and Privacy Management.</i>	V 1.3.1
ETSI TS 102 942	<i>Access control</i>	V 1.1.1
ETSI EN 302 890-2	<i>Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Facilities layer function; Part 2: Position and time facility specification</i>	V0.0.3 (draft)

Table 2 - ETSI Standards overview

In complement of ETSI standards, we can also refer to “Cooperative ITS Security Framework: standards and Implementations Progress in Europe” paper [2], which present standardization activities and implementations of security services in various cooperative driving applications (and mainly ETSI standards).

2.3.1 ETSI TR 102 893 V1.2.1

This standard applies TVRA (Threat, Vulnerability and Risk Analysis) method to communications in ITS systems. It identifies ITS-Ss, the communicating entities (vehicles, roadside units, and network infrastructure), the set of service applications within ITS-Ss, and the communication services. Then the TVRA consists in identifying security objectives that are derived in security requirements. An inventory of system assets is made, along with a classification of vulnerabilities and threats. As any other risk assessment method, it evaluates the likelihood and impact of attacks and determines the risks involved. The last result comes with countermeasures.

Countermeasure	Threats	Risk
Include an authoritative identity in each message and authenticate it	Masquerade as ITS-S (Vehicle or Roadside) or ITS network	Major

Table 3 - ETSI TR 102 893 V1.2.1 – Example of countermeasure

2.3.2 ETSI TS 102 731 V1.1.1

In the frame of ITS security services and architecture, this standard addresses credential and identity management, privacy and anonymity, integrity protection, authentication and authorization. It describes ITS authoritative hierarchy (manufacturer, enrolment authorities, authorization authorities), ITS security parameter management (identities and identifiers in ITS), message communication models (public/private messages and security associations between ITS-Ss), and the various ITS security services related to enrolment, authorization, integrity, accountability, etc.

2.3.3 ETSI TS 103 097 V1.3.1

This Standard describes in detail the Security Header added to a C-ITS message and also the certificate format. It specifies the handling of the security header, which contains the certificate information for authentication and integrity checks.

2.3.4 ETSI TS 102 940 V1.3.1

This standard describes in detail the ITS communication security architecture and security management. It therefore supports technical information on the security management defined within the Security Policy. It defines in detail the implementation of Communication Security Management for C-ITS Stations and lists the requirements by the architecture.

2.3.5 ETSI TS 102 941 V1.3.1

This standard specifies the Trust and Privacy Management for C-ITS. It focuses on providing trust and privacy related requirements for an ITS-S lifecycle and the Public Key Infrastructure.

2.3.6 ETSI TS 102 942 V1.1.1

This standard overviews the mechanisms to grant access control in ITS. It describes the authorization groups for CAM and DENM messages, and enumerates the authorization information required to validate the sender of these messages.

2.3.7 ETSI EN 302 890-2 V0.0.3

The ETSI EN 302 890-2 V0.0.3 (2019-03) PoTi early draft can be mentioned (Facilities Layer function Part 2: Facility Position and Time management (PoTi)). The POTI layer manages the position and time references that security layer uses.

2.4 C2C-CC

The Car-to-Car Communication Consortium (C2C-CC) contributes to the European standard for C-ITS communicating systems by describing supported ITS services, network protocols and architecture. It also provides safety, traffic and infotainment applications. The following figure depicts the C-ITS architecture proposed by the C2C-CC consortium.

Figure 2 – C2C-CC architecture model

2.5 PRESERVE SEVECOM

The SeVeCom [3] project described security architecture for Vehicular Communication systems. It focuses on authentication, integrity and privacy mechanisms, utilizing a combination of long-term and short-term (pseudonymous) credentials, issued by Certificate Authorities and managed by HSMS in the ITS-S.

The PRESERVE [4] project defined security architecture for V2X communications, based on previous and related projects, such as SeVeCom and C2C-CC. Reference architecture is given supporting vehicle stations, road side units, and central stations/servers. The project defines the main interfaces, cryptographic components and libraries used to preserve integrity, authenticity and privacy in the communications between the stated entities.

2.6 ISO/SAE 21434

This risk-oriented standard is under development at the time of writing this document. It addresses cyber-security during the full life cycle of road vehicles: engineering, production, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning. It defines a cyber-security process framework including requirements and a common language for communicating and managing cyber-security risk among stakeholders.

2.7 GDPR

To enforce data protection for individuals, a data privacy policy must be set by the vehicle. In Europe, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR [5]) allows data collection when its purpose is explicit and under individual consent. For cyber-security purpose, the consent is not mandatory since a cyber-security flaw may impact the human life. In any case, giving control back to individuals over their personal data is a best practice of data privacy management.

2.8 EU Directive 2016/1148 (NIS directive)

The NIS Directive establishes security and notification requirements for operators of essential services and for digital service providers). Road transport authorities and operators are considered

as operators of essential services. According to the definition given below, ITS operators have to comply with this directive.

	<p>Road authorities as defined in point (12) of Article 2 of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2015/962 [6] responsible for traffic management control: 'road authority' means any public authority responsible for the planning, control or management of roads falling within its territorial competence</p>
Road transport	<p>Operators of Intelligent Transport Systems as defined in point (1) of Article 4 of Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council: 'Intelligent Transport Systems' or 'ITS' means systems in which information and communication technologies are applied in the field of road transport, including infrastructure, vehicles and users, and in traffic management and mobility management, as well as for interfaces with other modes of transport;</p>

Table 4 - Road Transport - Operators of Essential Services

3 Overall Cyber-Security Architecture

As explained in the deliverable D3.1 of the ICT4CART project, safe and secure data exchanges with preserved personal data privacy are granted by modules pertaining to the Security and Privacy group. These modules gather Identity and Access Management, Cyber Security Supervision and Data Privacy functions.

Figure 3 – Functions required for ICT4CART use cases (from ICT4CART D3.1 deliverable)

These three modules are cloud services. They are detailed in chapters 4 and 5.

4 Cyber-Security Supervision Architecture

4.1 Role

The role of the cyber-security supervision service is to analyse cyber-security events collected from vehicles, RSUs, MEC servers and cloud services. It also assesses vulnerability against known flaws and exploits, complemented with threat knowledge. Major outputs of the analysis are cyber-security incidents that require to be considered by road operators, cities, car makers, OEMs and service providers. Periodic cyber-security activity and situation reports are relevant to get the big picture of the cyber-security health of a vehicle fleet, road infrastructure and parking management services for instance.

4.2 Actors

Several actors have been identified for the supervision service. They can be human beings and organisations, or systems. The figure below depicts these actors and the way they interact with the supervision service (one-way or two-way communication).

Interactions are defined taken the project use cases involving cyber-security into account.

Figure 4 – Supervision actors

- **Vehicle:** the supervision service collects messages and cyber-security events from vehicles. The supervision service also requests vehicles to apply some actions as part of cyber threat mitigation process. For example, decrease the vehicle automation level.
- **RSU:** the supervision service collects messages and cyber-security events from RSUs. Although RSUs could have been requested by the supervision service to enforce some actions, the foreseen implementation in test sites does not include such a case. That is why the RSU-supervision service channel is one-way. As a consequence, the supervision actors figure depicts this by a one-way arrow from the RSU to the supervision service.

- **MEC server:** the supervision service collects messages and cyber-security events from MEC servers. Although MEC servers could have been requested by the supervision service to enforce some actions, the foreseen implementation in test sites does not include such a case. That is why the RSU-supervision service channel is one-way. As a consequence, the supervision actors figure depicts this by a one-way arrow from the MEC server to the supervision service.
- **Cloud service:** the supervision service collects cyber-security events from cloud services. Although cloud services could have been requested by the supervision service to enforce some actions, the foreseen implementation in test sites does not include such a case. That is why the RSU-supervision service channel is one-way. As a consequence, the supervision actors figure depicts this by a one-way arrow from cloud services to the supervision service.
- **IAM service:** the supervision service collects cyber-security events from the IAM service. The supervision service also requests the IAM service to enforce actions such as certificate revocation. Finally the supervision service also registers to the IAM service as a communicating entity with ITS-S and IAM service.
- **Vulnerability and threat knowledge:** the supervision service collects vulnerability bulletins and threat information from a knowledge base maintained by another service (out of scope of the project).
- **Supervisor:** the supervisor is a user that connects to the service to check the cyber-security status of monitored entities and manages alerts and incidents.
- **Analyst:** the analyst is a user that connects to the service to analyse and bring expertise to ongoing alerts and incidents, providing support to the supervisor.
- **Administrator:** the administrator is a user that connects to the service to administrate it.
- **Operator:** the operator is a user that connects to the service to access cyber-security dashboards. He/she has subscribed the service to be aware of the situation of his/her organisation. The operator's organisation could be a road operator, a city, a car maker, an OEM or a service provider.
- **CERT/CSIRT:** CERTs/CSIRTs are public or private organisations in charge of major cyber-incident analysis and response. One of the basic NIS Directive purpose is to form (and strengthen) an overlay connecting the CERT/CSIRT authorities that should receive informative notifications of (past) security incidents. In this context, the supervision service can be accessed by allowed CERTs/CSIRTs to display a view on past major incidents.

4.3 Functional architecture

The supervision service has the following functionalities:

- **Collection:** Collecting data is the foundation of the cyber-security monitoring. This is a real-time and one-way process, from the data source to the collection point. Collected data may be security events from embedded or network sensors or ITS messages such as CAM, DENM, CPM, etc.
- **Detection:** The supervision service includes a rule-based correlation engine and an anomaly detection engine based on artificial intelligence.
- **Response orchestration:** The role of this capacity is to provide the necessary functions to cyber-security experts to **investigate** create an incident report and gather relevant information. It also interfaces with the **reaction enforcement** capacity to request incident mitigation countermeasures.
- **Reporting:** Various dashboards and reports are needed to be aware of the cyber situation. They are built by the reporting capacity based on stored data, including correlation alerts.
- **Linkability:** collected information may contain anonymised data to preserve privacy. However from a security point of view, and typically during the correlation process, it is

really important to be able to link events and messages due to data characteristics. The linkability function provides this capacity.

The figure below depicts the supervision service functional architecture.

Figure 5 – Functional architecture of the cyber-security supervision service

The supervision service functionalities are more deeply described in sub-chapters below.

4.3.1 Data collection

This component collects data from any source needed by the supervision service to assess the cyber-security situation and raise alerts. It also includes data normalisation, enrichment and storage capacities.

Figure 6 – Data collection – internal processes

4.3.1.1 Event and message collection

Event and message collection receives event logs and operational messages from ITS-S, services and servers. It has the ability to support various data formats including raw data and communication protocols over a security layer. Most common ways are Syslog, JSON/HTTP, XML/HTTP and JSON/AMQP. The collected data are normalised: the data content is analysed and its structure is deduced. This leads to distinguish a set of key/value pairs. This step is absolutely crucial for the other processes and functionalities.

Use cases involving supervision are focused on cyber-security events. Even considering only those events, the collection capacity has to be scalable when considering tens of thousands of vehicles, RSUs, applications as potential sources of data. Collection is a push-mode process to simplify the configuration: only the supervision service URL has to be known by an event sender. Events to be reported are pushed to the target service.

Assumption according to targeted scenarios:

- Germany: Applications and core IT services in the cloud and IAM service send events related to authentication and rights issues. Simulated BMW vehicles might do so as well.
- Italy: IAM service, MEC server and OBU could send events related to authentication and rights issues, and ITS messages

4.3.1.2 Data enrichment

Normalised data are enriched before being stored. The enrichment process consists in adding information from components dedicated to a specific knowledge. In the ICT4CART project context, the enrichment addresses threat and vulnerability information.

Example #1: From the vehicle model and version reported in an event message, the event enrichment tries to get additional information regarding the vehicle OBU software stack from a knowledge database shared by an OEM. Retrieved information is added to the event message.

Example #2: From the vehicle model and version reported in an event, and from the event type, the event enrichment tries to get threat entries that refer both values. The more detailed the filter is, the better is to get relevant threat information. For instance, in that case, the filter could have also mentioned the message type in the communication (e.g., CAM, DENM).

The enrichment process may also translate code values into concrete values.

Example #3: replace a status code by a string value. This has an interest for consistency in further analytics processes.

4.3.1.3 Vulnerability collection

Vulnerability collection gathers information about known vulnerability in operating systems, software or configuration. This information, called vulnerability bulletins, is available from various sources: solution vendors (e.g., Microsoft, Siemens), research centres, and specialised providers (free or charged).

Vulnerability bulletins are reports containing (but not limited to) the following information:

- Vulnerability description
- Vulnerability identifiers in the most common databases: Common Vulnerability Exposure (CVE) , Bugtraq
- Impacted components
- Identifiers of the impacted components according to the Common Pattern Enumeration (CPE) , a structured naming scheme
- Impact evaluation (Severity score and Metric)
- Recommendations to fix the vulnerability, if available

As explained in 4.3.1.2, the enrichment process benefits from this knowledge to automatically add

matches with collected events. Within the incident management phase, collected vulnerability information can also be requested by supervision users to check if a known vulnerability could have been exploited by a cyber-attacker.

4.3.1.4 Threat information collection

Cyber threat knowledge enables the event enrichment process to find matches between event data and threat data also known as indicators of compromise (IoCs). It is also used by supervisors and analysts to confirm an alert is a cyber-attack and to manually enrich it with relevant data. It may also be used during the event correlation process to draw similar conclusion in an automated way and thus save time in the analysis.

Maintaining threat knowledge is an activity performed by a dedicated team, out of the scope of cyber-security supervision. This activity roughly consists in retrieving threat information from various public and private sources, normalising and merging it into a threat intelligence platform (TIP). It includes information related to campaigns, targets, objectives, tactics and procedures used by attackers. It encompasses technical and non-technical information. This enables experts to discover, analyse and report cyber attacker activities.

4.3.1.5 Data storage

Due the scalability issue, this is the last process of the data collection capacity. Indeed, since data are not fully described and/or enriched, it would cost a lot of resources to save, update and save them multiple times. Use of NoSQL databases is preferred in this context.

4.3.2 Detection

The core function of a supervision system is the analysis of alerts from cyber-security sensors. They also highlight correlated alerts and enable supervision operators to investigate through dashboards. They can make cross-correlation to determine if there is an attempt to exploit vulnerability. In ICT4CART, the detection process is twofold: analyse cyber-security events coming from secure communications layers and services implemented in ITS-S, core and support services, the IAM service, etc. In parallel, try to find anomalies in a flow of messages whatever their nature. Example of anomalies: traffic jam warning by a single ITS-S collocated with other ITS-S not reporting such a situation. This may be the indication of a compromised or rogue ITS-S trying to disturb the traffic.

As explained in the chapter 4.3.1, events and messages are normalised, enriched and stored. Then both detection processes periodically pull these stored data.

Figure 7 – Detection

4.3.2.1 Event correlation

Event correlation is a rule-based process that aims at finding relationships in a set of events within a time window. Correlation rules describe cyber-security issues such as an attack or a situation at risk. These rules are built according to a detection strategy, generally derived from a risk analysis and from best practices. Event correlation is adapted to known and simple attacks, i.e. unsophisticated and easily detectable by systems' security layer or by dedicated sensors.

In the context of the ICT4CART use cases, correlation rules are focused on cyber-security events related to secure communications (e.g., bad credentials, unauthorised actions, etc.). These events may occur within ITS-S, services, etc. The foreseen implementation in test sites should limit the event sources to vehicles and cloud services.

There are several correlation rule types:

- Unitary events: This type of rule aims at alerting on critical and reliable events. It specifies values for a set of event fields (one value per field). If fields in a collected event fully match these values, then an alert is triggered.
- Aggregation of events: This type of rule is used to detect events occurring several times in a period. It could be used for instance to alert on massive phenomena. It finds similar events in a time range and counts the occurrence. An alert is triggered if the occurrence exceeds a threshold. Similarity is defined by identical values in a set of fields. Here are examples of aggregation rules.
 - o Rule #1 defines that vehicle events are similar if the following fields are identical: VIN, event type, event title.
 - o Rule #2 defines that vehicle events are similar if the following fields are identical: vehicle maker, vehicle model, event type, event title
- New event: This type of rule aims at detecting new or unusual events. The rule matches if an event does not share field values with any other events within a time window. The rule specifies what fields to look at.
- Change: This type of rule aims at detecting changes in repetitive events. The rule matches if an event has field values different from the last observed ones. The rule specifies what fields to look at.

- Absence of events: This type of rule aims at detecting the absence of events occurring frequently. The rule specifies an event and a time window, and it matches if it has not been seen in the time window.
- Blacklist: this rule specifies a list of unwanted values for a given field. The rule matches if a collected event gets one of these values
- Whitelist: this rule specifies a list of expected values for a given field. The rule matches if a collected event does not get one of these values
- Sequence of events: this rule specifies a list of events. If they are collected within a time window, then an alert is triggered.

Depending on the fields and the rule type, it will be necessary to check if some events share the same field values. In case of pseudonymised field values, it is not possible without a linkability capacity. That is why the correlation process requests the linkability component before applying correlation rules to an observed set of events.

The outcome of the correlation process is a correlation alert. It contains information from correlated events and from the rule (e.g., alert title). This content depends on the rule type. It may be relevant to try and complement the correlation alert by threat information. Consequently, a request to the threat collection component will be done after alert creation.

4.3.2.2 Anomaly detection

Event correlation relies on expected events and simple known situations. It is not effective for new and/or stealthy attacks. To mitigate this drawback, anomaly detection is a complementary process that will analyse collected data. Abnormal situations could be discovered by observing not only cyber-security events but also functional events (e.g., messages exchanged by ITS-S), and find links between them. This implies analysing a huge quantity of data and thus requires an adapted system.

The proposed anomaly detection works as follows:

- Events stored by the collection process are continuously retrieved
- Relevant features are extracted from events.
- Extracted features are converted into a numerical vector that machine learning algorithms can process.
- Outlier detection algorithms compute a vector anomaly score. A high score means the event is abnormal.
- High score events are stored as anomalies.

An anomaly is described through the following data: start and end time of the anomaly, anomaly identifier, anomaly type, a reference to involved events. An anomaly marker is also provided to describe the processing status of the anomaly. At detection stage, the marker is set to 0.

4.3.2.3 Correlation alert and anomaly storage

Due to the scalability issue, this is the last process of the detection capacity. The use of NoSQL databases is preferred in this context.

4.3.3 Response orchestration

Response orchestration is a rule-based process that aims at supporting supervision operators in the correlation alert and anomaly management. It computes the course of actions that should be enforced to mitigate the cyber issue impact.

In certain situations and depending on the criticality of the incident and the specific context, an automatic reaction can be also triggered.

Figure 8 – Orchestration

4.3.3.1 Context evaluation

This computation is based on the evaluation of the cyber-security and road context: type of the cyber-security issue, types and count of targets, level of automation, etc.

4.3.3.2 Research of Courses of Actions (COA)

This research is based on the context evaluated in the previous phase and on predefined associations with CoA made within a preparation phase (cf. chapter 4.3.3.3).

4.3.3.3 Management of Courses of Actions

Courses of actions are defined by experts. They also depend on a reaction policy defined by the organisation subscribing to the supervision service. Actions may consist in getting additional knowledge, requesting focused investigation, warning operators and third-parties, and enforcing actions on systems. CoAs are associated to cyber-security issue contexts.

4.3.3.4 Access control

Access control is described in chapter 4.4.1.

4.3.4 Investigation

Investigation comes after the detection process, and may be required by the orchestration process. After an automated analysis, the released information (alert or anomaly) is processed by a cyber-security expert who has to confirm the incident and determines its criticality. The expert may provide recommendations on how to mitigate the incident impact as well.

Figure 9 – Investigation

4.3.4.1 Incident qualification

The main activities within the incident qualification process are:

- Analyse anomalies: Tag anomalies as true positives or false positives
- Analyse events and alerts
- Create an incident report from a set of related anomalies, events and correlation alerts
- Add comments, files, references that support the analysis
- Find out the attack scenario
- Recommend mitigation and corrective actions

4.3.4.2 Incident storage

Created incident reports are stored. The amount of incidents and the many joint data makes the use of SQL databases relevant.

4.3.4.3 Access control

Access control is described in chapter 4.4.1.

4.3.5 Reaction enforcement

Reaction enforcement is driven by the orchestration. It starts by selecting the course of actions (CoA) to mitigate the impact of a cyber-security incident, and is followed by the enforcement of actions by users or systems. The selection of the CoA and even some actions within the CoA may be enforced automatically.

Note: in the ICT4CART project, the implementation of reaction enforcement capacities will be restricted to vehicles and the IAM service, which explains why the diagram below only designates vehicles and the IAM service as enforcement points for external actions.

Figure 10 – Reaction enforcement

4.3.5.1 CoA instantiation

The instantiation of the course of actions is the selection of the most suitable course of actions among those proposed within the orchestration. This selection may be automatically done or may be done by the supervisor or the analyst. Actions may have to be done by supervision service users. In this case, they are described as procedures. They may be performed by components of the supervision service or by external systems as well.

4.3.5.2 Actions enforcement

Procedures and component actions are internal actions. Both component and external system actions may be configured to be automatically enforced. For example, in case of a confirmed cyber-attack on vehicles approaching a toll gate, the CoA could specify to automatically lower the level of vehicle automation and warns the road infrastructure operator managing the toll gate. Another example: in the same context, the CoA could specify to automatically warn the road infrastructure operator and recommend it to request the decrease of level of vehicle automation.

In the foreseen implementation of the ICT4CART use cases, external systems requested to enforce actions will be the IAM service, and vehicles. Neither test nor demonstration will be performed with RSUs and cloud services.

4.3.5.3 Incident enrichment

A course of actions is an action tree managed through a workflow. This one depends on action enforcement results. Results are retrieved, analysed and kept in the incident database. They are used as preconditions by subsequent actions. They are also used to inform supervision service users.

4.3.5.4 Access control

Access control is described in chapter 4.4.1.

4.3.6 Reporting

The reporting component establishes and displays the cyber-security situation, and provides views of collected and computed information throughout the various processes of the supervision service.

Figure 11 – Reporting

4.3.6.1 Situation dashboard

Dashboards are produced for an operator in order to display the cyber-security situation. Dashboards can be configured to fit the activity of the operator. Dashboards for OEMs will be different from Road operators or cities. However they all deal with high-level information. That is why there is no link with the event storage. Information displayed will focus on trends regarding anomalies and alerts: evolution, dispatch by anomaly/alert category, dispatch by target, etc. Information on incidents may be more detailed as they probably involve operators as being warned or even active stakeholders. This kind of reporting can be considered like a communication portal with operators.

4.3.6.2 Event, correlation alert, anomaly and incident views

They are views built from detailed information to support analysis, investigation, and incident management by supervisors and analysts. They are basically tables of events, correlation alerts, anomalies and incidents. The incident view also integrates management features, like courses of actions selection and enforcement.

To comply with the NIS directive, CERT and CSIRT may have an access to the incident view with restrictions: view of past incidents only, with no addition, modification or deletion rights. CERT/CSIRT. Note that another interface could have been based on standards such as IODEF or STIX/TAXII to send incident reports to CERTs/CSIRTs. This interface will not be described because it will not be implemented.

4.3.6.3 Access control

Access control is described in chapter 4.4.1.

4.4 Support capacities

4.4.1 Access control

The collection of data needs to use a secured channel. The implementation of ITS-S standards grants this security from any ITS-S willing to transmit cyber-security events or messages. Then the supervision service can be considered as an ITS-S receiving data. On the other hand, the IAM service and the core services will also transmit events to the supervision service. They will do so through a TLS channel.

An access control is necessary for communications secured with TLS and related to access to supervision applications and data. It deals with any user connecting the supervision service. Cf. chapter 4.5.8.

4.4.2 Linkability

Collected data is unlinkable by default and, only when necessary, it can be processed to allow linking messages coming from the same entity. With this approach, data privacy is ensured by default, while allowing extracting utility out of it.

This functionality is provided through Group Signatures with Selective Linkability (GSSL). Entities can obtain a pseudonymous credential through a Group Manager and create pseudonymous and unlinkable signatures. These signatures can be verified by anyone, without learning the identity of the specific signer. A posteriori, these pseudonymously signed messages can be linked through a Converter entity. The Converter receives a list of pseudonym and (encrypted) message pairs, and converts all pseudonyms consistently, so that all pseudonyms originating from the same entity are mapped to the same converted pseudonym.

Note that this linkability is only offered and is efficient to process data that has been previously stored along with the corresponding pseudonymous signatures. This can be used, for instance, to detect anomalous behaviour from logged data in a privacy preserving manner. Specifically, this type of linkability is not aimed at implementing access control through authorization or revocation capabilities.

4.5 External interfaces

Several external interfaces are necessary to collect information, enable access to users and request action enforcement. They are described in subchapters below.

4.5.1 Cyber-security event collection interface

Events related to communication security (e.g., unauthorized modification attempt, unknown CA, etc.) are reported to the supervision service by the entities involved in automated driving.

Transmitted data may contain various kinds of information: at least, a timestamp, an anonymised yet linkable identifier of the reporting device, a description of the issue, the location, the device type and the source of the issue.

Figure 12 – Cyber-security event collection interfaces

Event messages from ITS-S are sent through HTTP and are secured in compliance with the ITS-S standards. Event messages from cloud services, the IAM service and MEC servers are sent through HTTP and are secured with TLS.

4.5.2 ITS-S message collection interface

The anomaly detection capacity works on messages out of cyber-security events. As the foreseen use case to implement cyber-security services is the smart parking use case, messages that can be collected are restricted to this use case. Depending on the test site, ITS-S messages are collected directly or from MEC servers. Data from traffic and parking services are also relevant to detect anomalies.

Actually there are two points of collections that depend on the communication transport protocol used.

Figure 13 – ITS-S message collection interface

Requests are made through HTTP and are secured in compliance with the ITS-S standards.

4.5.3 Threat information collection interface

To let the correlation engine, supervisors and analysts benefit from threat knowledge, an interface to a TIP is set.

Depending on the architecture choice (cf. chapter 4.3.3.1), either the supervision service requests the remote TIP about new information since the previous request to feed its local base, or the supervision service requests the TIP each time some fields of a cyber-security event need to be compared with known indicators of compromise (IoCs) stored in a remote base.

In the first case (Figure 14), the timestamp of the previous request is sent to the threat knowledge service. The response contains the update.

Figure 14 – Threat information interface – Synchronize a local base

In the second case (Figure 15), the field type and value to check are sent to the threat knowledge service. The response contains the conclusion of the threat knowledge (known/unknown) and information about the attacker if there is match.

Figure 15 – Threat information interface – remote base

The protocol used for this interface depends on the TIP. Usually a TIP proposes a REST API. In that case, requests are made through HTTP and are secured with TLS. Certificates are managed by the PKI as described in section 5.3.1.

4.5.4 Vulnerability bulletin collection interface

Similarly to the threat base, the vulnerability knowledge base is either remote or local. This depends on an organisation decision.

In the case when the vulnerability used in the correlation and analysis processes is local, then the interface consists in synchronizing it with a remote system.

Figure 16 – Vulnerability information interface – Synchronize a local base

In the case when the vulnerability base is remote with no local base, then the interface consists in a requester called each time that an event needs to be checked against the vulnerability base. In case of a match, details regarding the vulnerability are provided.

Figure 17 – Vulnerability information interface – remote base

The protocol used for this interface depends on the vulnerability knowledge solution. More and more such solutions propose a REST API. In that case, requests are made through HTTP and are secured with TLS. Certificates are managed by the PKI as described in chapter 5.

4.5.5 Enrolment and authorisation interface

As the supervision service may request ITS-S for action enforcement, it has to support ITS-S communication means. Then it can be seen as an ITS-S. Consequently it is compliant with standards such as ETSI 102940 and 102941. Therefore it needs to get enrolled and authorised to communicate with ITS-S by the IAM service.

The interface is twofold: first it enables the supervision service to send its canonical identity and retrieve enrolment credentials. Secondly it enables the supervision service to get an authorisation ticket giving its enrolment credentials.

Figure 18 – Enrolment & authorization interface

Requests are made through HTTP and are secured in compliance with the ITS-S standards.

4.5.6 IAM service action interface

As part of a course of actions subsequent to an alert, the supervision service may request the IAM service to perform some action. One of them is the revocation of an ITS-S' certificate which may happen to prevent a rogue ITS-S or a compromised ITS-S to communicate with other ITS-S. The principle is to send the type of requested action along with the targeted ITS-S. This supposes that both supervision and IAM services share an ITS-S identification means. The response provided by the IAM service is the result of the action (e.g., return code).

Figure 19 – IAM service action interface

Requests are made through HTTP and are secured with TLS. Certificates are managed by the PKI as described in chapter 5.

4.5.7 ITS-S action interface

As part of a course of actions subsequent to an alert, the supervision service may request an ITS-S to perform some action. The principle is to send the type of requested action and its associated parameters. The response

provided by the ITS-S is the result of the action (e.g., return code).

Figure 20 – ITS-S action interfaces

Requests are made through HTTP and are secured in compliance with the ITS-S standards.

4.5.8 Supervision application interface

Users of the supervision service connect through a web browser. They are allowed to access views and functions depending on their role that is verified by the IAM service.

Figure 21 – Supervision application interface

Requests are made through HTTP and are secured with TLS. Certificates are managed by the PKI as described in chapter 5.

4.5.9 Linkability Converter interface

The Converter offers an internal interface to the Supervision service, so that the latter can process pseudonymously signed messages.

When required, a list of pairs of blinded messages and pseudonyms is sent to the Converter. The Converter then returns a converted list, where all pseudonyms originating from the same entity have been consistently mapped to a common representation.

Figure 22 – Linkability converter interface

4.6 Relationship with communication and data (IT) architectures

In the project deliverable D3.3, “IT Environment Specification and Architecture” [7], an off-board access to data by cloud services is proposed to get compliant with the Extended Vehicle (ExVe) Concept [8]. If an off-board access to data is implemented then the supervision service, as a cloud service, could collect vehicle event and message data from this capacity. In that case, the event and message collection module within the data collection capacity will pull data from the off-board facility instead of directly receiving data from vehicles.

5 IAM Service and Data Privacy Architecture

5.1 Role

The role of the Identity and Access Management (IAM) service is to provide authentication and authorization functionalities to ITS-S and Users.

The mechanisms used for ITS-S also allow ensuring privacy and confidentiality.

5.2 Actors

Several actors have been identified for the IAM service. They can be human beings and organisations, or systems. The figure below depicts these actors and the way they interact with the IAM service.

Interactions are defined taken the project use cases involving cyber-security into account.

Figure 23 – IAM actors

- **ITS-S (Vehicle, RSU, etc)**: the IAM service provides authentication and authorizations for ITS-S who need to access to ITS communications and services.
- **Administrator**: the administrators are users who have rights to administrate the IAM service. They have access to the administration application, from which they can manage users and devices and their rights.
- **Users of services (Operator, Supervisor, etc)**: other users (non IAM administrator) need the IAM service to authenticate them and authorize them to access other services. For example, a supervisor who needs to access the supervision service should be authenticated by the IAM service before.
- **Supervision service**: the supervision service collects cyber-security events from the IAM

service. The supervision service also requests the IAM service to enforce actions such as certificate revocation. Finally the supervision service also registers to the IAM service as a communicating entity with ITS-S and IAM service.

- **Other PKI services:** The IAM service provides a PKI for ITS-S certificates needs. To be compatible with all ITS-S, the IAM service needs to have trust relationship with other PKI services (PKI from other manufacturer, other country, etc.)

5.3 Functional architecture

The figure below depicts the supervision service functional architecture.

Figure 24 – Functional architecture of IAM service

5.3.1 PKI

The PKI's architecture follows the ETSI standard and integrates the following part:

- Root CA (RCA): Highest level CA in the certification chain.
- Enrolment Authority (EA): Deliver enrolment credential to authenticate and grant access to ITS communications
- Authorization Authority (AA): Deliver authorization tickets (or pseudonym certificates) to authorize the use of specific ITS services. ITS-S that requests for authorization tickets have to be already enrolled by the EA.

Figure 25 – PKI architecture

This separation of duties allows ensuring the privacy of ITS-S. Only the EA know the identity information of ITS-S.

The PKI generates and manages certificate regarding the IEEE Std 1609.2 standard.

5.3.2 Users Access module

5.3.2.1 Authentication

The Authentication module offers authentication functions based the following methods:

- OpenID Connect : the module can consume a token from an external federated OpenID provider in order to authenticate a user on the platform
- SAMLv2 : the module can consume an assertion from a SAML Identity Provider in order to authenticate a user
- Login / password : the module can authenticate a user based on a user account known into the IAM Directory
- Certificate : the module can authenticate a user based on a certificate issued by a configured Certificate Authority

In accordance to OpenID Connect specification, the result of the authentication phase is based on 2 JSON Web Token:

- An access token (contains the rights)
- An identity token

This module receives identity information, validates them, and generates access token.

5.3.2.2 Authorization

The authorization module offers access control and web request filtering capabilities based on rights contained in the token.

All accesses to services by users are done through this module, which one guaranty that a user is authorized to request the service.

5.3.3 IAM Directory

IAM Directory is the identities and rights referential. All users, devices and their rights are stored into this directory.

The content is managed from the Administration application, and the different authentication and authorization functionalities are based on this directory.

This directory can be also used by other services like a centralized referential of identities.

5.3.4 Administration Application

Administration application provides an application to manage users, devices and right models. From this application, an administrator can activate or deactivate a device, and revoke a certificate.

5.3.5 Linkability Manager

The Linkability Manager is the Authority issuing pseudonymous credentials for users and devices to be able to issue pseudonymous signatures that can be linked as specified in Section 4.4.2. Prior to issuing a pseudonymous credential, the Linkability Manager authenticates the requester using any of the accepted authentication mechanisms. Note that as a result of this process, all entities share the same public key, but each will have obtained its own private credential enabling it to issue pseudonymous signatures.

The pseudonymous signatures issued by means of these pseudonymous credentials are aimed at enabling data processing after the data has been collected. Specifically, they are not intended to be used for authorization purposes. The lifetime of pseudonymous credentials may be defined according to the use case needs, requiring the ITS-S to request a new pseudonymous credential when the old one is expired.

5.4 External interfaces

5.4.1 Linkability Service Manager

In order to allow new entities to obtain pseudonymous credentials, the Linkability Service Manager exposes an interface listening to new join requests. After some message exchange, authorized entities receive the pseudonymous credentials.

Figure 26 – Linkability manager interface

5.4.2 ITS-S Authentication

Prerequisite before using ITS communications, an ITS-S must request the Enrolment Authority in IAM service to be authenticated. The ITS-S sends to the Enrolment Authority its canonical identity and gets in return an enrolment credentials.

Figure 27 – ITS-S Enrolment interface

Then, the ITS-S can request the Authorization Authority with the enrolment credentials getting previously. The Authorization Authority returns the authorization tickets.

Figure 28 – ITS-S Authorization interface

Requests are sent through HTTP and are secured in compliance with the ITS-S standards.

5.4.3 Users Authentication

First step of all actions made by users on any services, the authentication will deliver to user an identity token and an access token. The authentication module supports different types of authentication methods (login/password, certificate, federation protocol like OpenID connect or SAMLv2, etc.).

Figure 29 – Users Authentication interface

The authorization module is in front of any service which needs to be protected and use the access token to check the rights for a user to access a service.

Figure 30 – Users Authorization interface

Requests are sent through HTTP and are secured with TLS.

5.4.4 IAM application

A user with administrator profile can access to IAM administration application to manage IAM data (users, ITS-S, rights model, etc.).

This application is protected by the authorisation module.

Figure 31 – IAM application interface

Requests are sent through HTTP and are secured with TLS.

5.4.5 Supervision Service

Each modules of the IAM service generate security events (authentication error, unauthorised access, rights modification, etc.). These events are sent to the supervision service. Each event contains at least, a timestamp, the source of the event, the pseudonym identity of the device, and the event message.

Figure 32 – Supervision service interface

Event messages are sent through HTTP and are secured with TLS.

5.4.6 Trust list manager

As described in the ETSI standards, in case of many Root CA used, the Trust list manager is the entity allowing to all Root CAs to trust each other. Any Root CA can request the Trust list manager to get the Certificate Trust List, which contains the list of all Root CA trusted.

Figure 33 – Trust list manager interface

Note: This interface will not be implemented in any use case.

6 Sequence diagrams

6.1 IAM Directory administration

This diagram depicts the sequence of actions to administrate the IAM directory used by the IAM service within the various phases of enrolment and authorisation.

Figure 34 – Declaration of new ITS-S

Note: The administration application is protected by the authorization module. This module does not appear in this diagram. For the generic sequence diagram of user authentication and authorization, see chapter 6.2.2

6.2 Initialisation

In this chapter diagrams explain how an ITS-S or a user authenticates as a first step of any communication.

6.2.1 ITS-S Authentication

Figure 35 – ITS-S Authentication

Note: ITS-S could be a vehicle, a RSU, a MEC server, a cloud service, etc.

6.2.2 User Authentication

Figure 36 – User Authentication

6.3 Renewal of credentials

In compliance with automotive standards, credentials have to be periodically renewed. The diagrams hereunder describe the sequence for the three types of credentials necessary for communication by actors in ICT4CART use cases.

6.3.1 Enrolment credentials

Figure 37 – Enrolment credentials renewal

6.3.2 Pseudonymous credentials

Figure 38 – Pseudonymous credentials renewal

6.3.3 Authorization ticket

Figure 39 – Authorization ticket renewal

6.4 Revocation

This diagram depicts the sequence of actions within the revocation of enrolment credentials.

Figure 40 – Enrolment credential revocation

Note: the supervision service may also be the requester for credential revocation.

6.5 Supervision service administration

The supervision service needs detection rulesets and predefined courses of actions. The sequence diagram hereunder depicts the related actions.

Figure 41 – Supervision service administration

6.6 Cyber-security event processing

This chapter describes the sequences of actions related to event processing by the supervision service. It starts by the collection of an event log emitted by a vehicle and ends by the storage of the incident report resulting from correlation with information including other events and investigation by cyber-security experts. Data stored for a long time are deleted by a periodical process.

6.6.1 Event correlation

Figure 42 – Event processing up to correlation

Note: sources of events are not restricted to vehicles. They may be ITS-S, MEC servers or cloud services.

6.6.2 Response and investigation

Figure 43 – Response and investigation

6.7 Message processing

The diagram in this chapter depicts how collected messages are processed by the supervision service. Even if event collection is not shown here, events are also used by the anomaly detection along with messages. Once anomalies are stored, they are processed in the same way correlation alerts are. Old stored data are deleted by a periodical process. Cf. chapter 4 for details on response and investigation sequence diagram.

Figure 44 – Message processing

7 Relevance with requirements

In this section, we check that all the requirements defined in the deliverable D2.3 have been addressed by the ICT4CART functional architecture described in this deliverable.

The table 5 below summarizes for each requirement which functions of the proposed architecture address it.

ID	Name	Description	Supervision					Data Privacy					
			Data collection	Detection	Response orchestration	Investigation	Reaction enforcement	Reporting	PKI	User Access module	IAM Directory	Administration Application	Linkability Manager
R-CY-1	IAM service - Pseudonymity	The IAM service shall grant pseudonymity of any enrolled ITS-S in provisioned authorization tickets							X				X
R-CY-2	ITS-S Pseudonym Certificate	The ITS-S shall provide a mechanism for changing frequently the ITS-S pseudonym certificate							X				X
R-CY-3	Authenticity in hybrid communication	Authentication of an ITS message shall be achieved over the Security Header.							X				

ID	Name	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
R-CY-4	Security Header	The Security Header shall be the same regardless which communication network is used.							X				
R-CY-5	Certificate formats	The format of certificates used in communications shall be of type EtsiTs103097Certificate							X				
R-CY-6	V2X Authentication Encryption	V2X communication means shall integrate authentication and encryption components.							X				
R-CY-7	RSU Authentication Encryption	RSU communication means shall integrate authentication and encryption components.							X				
R-CY-8	MEC Server Authentication Encryption	MEC server communication means shall integrate authentication and encryption components.							X				
R-CY-9	Cloud Service Authentication Encryption	Cloud service communication means shall integrate authentication and encryption components.							X	X			

ID	Name	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
R-CY-10	ITS-S and Service Authentication	Any ITS-S or services shall authenticate itself to another communicating ITS-S or service							X	X			
R-CY-11	ITS-S and Service Authorization	Any ITS-S or service shall permit only authenticated and authorized entities (users or applications) to share information and/or claim priority							X	X	X		
R-CY-12	ITS-S and Service Authorization to Restricted Information	Any ITS-S or service shall permit only authenticated and authorized entities (users or applications) to access and/or modify restricted information							X	X	X		

ID	Name	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
R-CY-13	ITS-S and Service Registry to IAM Service	Any ITS-S or service shall be registered in the IAM service, along with its rights.									X	X	
R-CY-14	ITS-S and Service Restricted Information	Any ITS-S or service shall provide a means of designating certain information as restricted									X		
R-CY-15	ITS-S Information Modification and Deletion	An ITS-S shall permit only authorized ITS applications to modify or delete ITS-S information							X	X	X		
R-CY-16	IAM Service - Scalability	The IAM service shall be scalable so that it can supervise an entire vehicle fleet	<p>These requirements will be addressed when technological solutions will be chosen. It will be clarified in WP6.</p>										
R-CY-17	Communication Security - Low Latency	The overhead in communication due to security layer shall not involve unacceptable latency											

ID	Name	Description	Supervision					Data Privacy					
R-CY-18	Protection of personal data - Permission	The protection of personal data should be in accordance with the GDPR regarding the user identity and data sharing									X		X
R-CY-19	Protection of personal data - Obfuscation	The protection of personal data should be in accordance with the GDPR regarding the user identity and data obfuscation									X		X
R-CY-20	Protection of personal data - Processing	The cyber-security services should collect only data that are adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for both managing access control and detecting cyber-security anomalies	X								X		
R-CY-21	Protection of personal data - Storage	The cyber-security services should have means to delete stored data, and particularly personal data. These means should be automated for data that no longer have to be kept.	X	X		X					X	X	

ID	Name	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
R-CY-22	Protection of personal data - Linkability of anonymised data used by the supervision service	The supervision service should be able to link collected data from anonymised fields, with no possibility by a third-party to link them.		X									X
R-CY-23	Supervision - IAM Service Cyber-security Issue Reporting	Any cyber-security issue regarding ITS-S enrolment or re-enrolment shall be reported by the IAM service to the supervision service.	X						X				
R-CY-24	Supervision - Access Control Gateway Issue Reporting	Any cyber-security issue regarding ITS-S authorization shall be reported by the Access Control Gateway to the supervision service.	X							X			
R-CY-25	Supervision - ITS-S Cyber-security Issue Reporting	Any cyber-security issue regarding authentication, access and modification within an ITS-S should be reported by this system to the supervision service as an event.	X					X	X		X		

ID	Name	Description	Supervision					Data Privacy					
R-CY-26	Supervision - ITS-S Reporting of Incoming and Outgoing Messages	Any incoming or outgoing message to/from an ITS-S may be reported by this system to the supervision service as an event.	X										
R-CY-27	Supervision - Service Provider Gateway Cyber-security Issue Reporting	Any detected cyber-security issue should be reported by the service provider gateway to the supervision service as an event.	X										
R-CY-28	Supervision - Information Collected by the Service Provider Gateway	The information collected by the Service Provider Gateway should be accessible to the supervision service in order to support the anomaly detection	X	X									

ID	Name	Description	Supervision					Data Privacy					
R-CY-29	Supervision - Personal Data Management	Personal data handled in the supervision centre shall be managed according to EU regulations	X	X		X							
R-CY-30	Supervision - Detection of cyber attacks	The supervision service shall be able to detect known attacks on communications		X									
R-CY-31	Supervision - Relevant BSA information	The supervision service may have access to information provided by vehicle basic set of application (BSA) services (ex: media file download)	X										
R-CY-32	Supervision - Detection of anomalies in communications	The supervision service shall be able to detect anomalies on communications		X									
R-CY-33	Supervision - Investigation capacity	The supervision service should be able to provide an investigation capacity on collected information				X							
R-CY-34	Supervision - Decision support	The supervision service should be able to determine the appropriate course of actions to mitigate a cyber-security issue affecting communications			X								
R-CY-35	Supervision - Enforcement of a course of actions	The supervision service may be able to request the IAM service to enforce actions related to detected cyber-attacks.			X		X					X	

ID	Name	Description	Supervision					Data Privacy					
R-CY-36	Supervision - Metrics	The supervision service should provide the following metrics: - number of vehicles/users/infrastructure devices/services impacted by an incident - services dependent of a service impacted by an incident - categories of reported incidents - geolocation of reported incidents - duration of reported incidents						X					
R-CY-37	Supervision - Mitigation Metrics	The supervision service may provide the following metrics: - distribution of suggested mitigation measures - distribution of automatic mitigation actions taken - distribution of incidents with and without suggested measures and automatic actions						X					
R-CY-38	Supervision - Impact Evaluation	The supervision service should evaluate the impact of a cyber-security incident with regard to the number of entities impacted, duration and geolocation						X					

ID	Name	Description	Supervision					Data Privacy				
R-CY-39	Supervision service - Scalability	The cyber-security supervision service shall be scalable so that it can supervise an entire vehicle fleet	X									
MN01	Privacy on Automated driving Market guidelines (D2.2)	Privacy minimum level of requirements performance level: 4 - Majority of services could operate with anonymised private user information.	X	X		X			X			X
MN07	Privacy on Informed journeys Market guidelines (D2.2)	Privacy minimum level of requirements performance level: 3 – Private user information can be anonymised for these services.	X	X		X			X			X
MN13	Privacy on Intelligent management Market guidelines (D2.2)	Privacy minimum level of requirements performance level: 4 – Personally identifiable information will be used by some services, but it may be possible to anonymise it.	X	X		X			X			X
MN20	Privacy on Coordination of vehicles Market guidelines (D2.2)	Privacy minimum level of requirements performance level: 2 – Private or sensitive information will not be transferred if services are designed as such.	X						X			X

ID	Name	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
MN26	Privacy on Connected travellers Market guidelines (D2.2)	Privacy minimum level of requirements performance level: 4 - Personally identifiable information is transferred.	X						X				X
MN32	Privacy on Underpinning Communication Services Market guidelines (D2.2)	Privacy minimum level of requirements performance level: 5 – Private user information is intrinsic to some of these services and there is a significant risk of security breaches.	X						X				X

Table 5 – Relevance with requirements

8 Relevance with standards and regulations

The following section aims at summarizing the functions of the proposed architecture that meet the requirements from the standards and regulations introduced in section 2.

Standards/ Regulations	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
		Data collection	Detection	Response orchestration	Investigation	Reaction enforcement	Reporting	PKI	User Access module	IAM Directory	Administration Application	Linkability Manager
Certificate Policy for Deployment and Operation of European Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS), V1.1								X				X
Security Policy & Governance Framework for Deployment and Operation												
ETSI TR 102 893 V1.2.1	Threat, Vulnerability and Risk Analysis (TVRA)	X						X	X	X	X	X

Standards/ Regulations	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
ETSI TS 102 731 V1.1.1	Security Services and Architecture	X		X		X		X	X		X	
ETSI TS 103 097 v1.3.1	Security header and certificate formats							X				
ETSI TS 102 940 V1.3.1	ITS communications security architecture and security management							X				X
ETSI TS 102 941 v1.3.1	Trust and Privacy Management							X	X			
ETSI TS 102 942 V1.1.1	Access control							X	X	X		
C2C - CC												
PRESERVE SEVECOM												

Standards/ Regulations	Description	Supervision						Data Privacy				
ISO/SAE 21434												
Regulation (EU) 2016/679	General Data Protection Regulation	X	X		X					X	X	X
EU Directive 2016/1148	NIS Directive	X	X		X		X	X	X		X	

Table 6 – Relevance with standards and regulations

9 Conclusion

The ICT4CART Cyber-Security and Data Privacy Specification, described in this document, addresses the challenges to enable automated driving from a cyber-security point of view. It presents a functional architecture that can be used to cover the listed requirements of the deliverable D2.3 and applies to all ICT4CART use cases and beyond.

This deliverable, therefore, first presented existing European standards and regulations that rule the automotive sector. This was followed by a functional view of the architecture, describing functional components of the supervision and the data privacy services. We also made explicit their interactions with each other and with external interfaces through sequence diagrams. Then we checked that all requirements related to cyber-security and data privacy have effectively been covered by the architecture proposed in this deliverable. Finally we summarized the standards and regulations addressed by each proposed function.

The proposed architecture addresses all the requirements defined in the ICT4CART deliverable D2.3 [9] except those related to latency and IAM service scalability. They will be considered in the implementation phase while applicable technologies will be evaluated. Addressed standards and regulations gather ETSI Standards for secured communications, GDPR for privacy concerns and NIS Directive for the supervision based on event logs. This cyber-security architecture is generic as the D3.1 architecture is. However the configuration of implemented systems will be different from a test site to another. For example, in the supervision service, log parsers will depend on systems emitting event logs (the format may be different). Correlation rules will be adapted to the contexts that may occur in each test site. Some specific dashboards may be required by one the users of a test site. In the IAM service, the rights of enrolled systems and users may be different for each test site.

The deliverable D3.4 will be used as an input for the WP6 dedicated to development and integration of cyber-security solutions for enhanced cyber-security supervision and data privacy for automated driving purposes.

10 References

- [1] [https://standards.iso.org/ittf/PubliclyAvailableStandards/s014258_ISO_IEC_7498-4_1989\(E\).zip](https://standards.iso.org/ittf/PubliclyAvailableStandards/s014258_ISO_IEC_7498-4_1989(E).zip)
- [2] <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7523576>
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- [8] ISO 20078-1:2019, Road vehicles — Extended vehicle (ExVe) web services — Part 1: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:20078:-1:ed-1:v1:en>: accessed on 13 June 2019.
- [9] "System Requirements", ICT4CART deliverable D2.3. June 2019.